

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th April 2021

Accepted: 27th April 2021

Online: 29th April 2021

KEY WORDS

British concept, culturology, distance, etiquette, Nobel prize, philosophy, pluralism, privacy, renaissance

The concept of England has a rich history and is associated with the heritage of such ancient European peoples as the Celts, Germans and Scandinavians. Anglo-Saxon concept had a huge impact on neighboring states, but also stepped far beyond the British Isles, becoming the basis for the globalized concept of the USA, Canada, Australia and many other countries of the world. The highest achievement of the concept of England today, without a doubt, can be considered the generally recognized giving the English language the status of the language of international communication. Since the end of 18th till the beginning of the 20th century British Empire being the main powerhouse of the world impacted the lifestyles of most countries of the world.

This article is conducted about the concept of culture, philosophy, manners and customs of the English people; It introduces the traditions and cultures of England.

And, in my opinion, this article will prove to be an indispensable assistant for those who are going to travel abroad.

THE ENGLISH CONCEPT IN PHILOSOPHY

Shigabutdinova Dina Yasavievna ¹, Hasanova Halida Fattoevna ²

¹ Bukhara State University, Lecturer, Independent researcher, faculty of foreign languages(ESP), Natural sciences department

² Lecturer, faculty of foreign languages(ESP), Natural sciences department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4732891>

ABSTRACT

The epoch of Victorian Britain is characterized by the rapid changes in Iron, Ornament and Architecture . Despite its underrepresented in the population of the world the people from England hold second number after the representatives of US in the number of Nobel prize holders.

“Concept are defined as common notions in speech or thoughts. The study of concept has approach called cognitive science.

Philosophy of Culture - a section of theoretical cultural studies, which explores the concept, essence and structure of culture, determines its function in society. Cultural studies as a science arose in the middle of the twentieth century, however, as a separate branch of knowledge, it began to form at the end of the nineteenth century, by separating it from the philosophy of culture. Therefore, the philosophy of culture performs methodological functions in relation to cultural studies, this is its foundation, basis, the first section of theoretical cultural studies. The term “philosophy of culture” was first introduced at the beginning of the 19th century by German philosopher A. Müller[1].

Philosophy of culture is “designation of approaches to the study essence, goals and values of culture, its conditions and forms of manifestation. It has a huge number of forms and often turns out to be identical to the

philosophy of history, since it is history that is considered as the process of unfolding and embodying the meaning of culture”[2].

In addition, in the spiritual part, many cultures can be quite close to each other, while in the interactional part, these same cultures reveal serious differences (cf. British and American culture, the culture of Germany and Austria). That is why cultural specificity should be traced not only in the material and / or spiritual, but also in the interactional, that is, in how the joint activities of people are organized to achieve a certain goal [3].

British civilization is a separate world, formed on the basis of the traditions of the peoples who inhabited the numerous islands, regions and provinces of the United Kingdom. It is a multicultural state with sovereignty over 14 overseas territories and 3 crown lands.

In the culture of continental Europe there is a tendency towards Unity, monism in religion, philosophy, and worldview as a whole (Catholicism, patriotism, socialism ...), in England there is a cult of privacy (privacy): “my home is my fortress”. The Englishman wants to define himself - in faith, in ideas, and in the style of life and way of life. There is no norm of a human character, on the contrary, multiplicity and diversity are honored.

The plays of William Shakespeare (1564-1616) entered the repertoire of the world theater and to this day occupy one of the first places in the posters. The device of the theater, for which Shakespeare wrote, the so-called “Elizabethan scene” (named after the queen who reigned at that time) for many years became an example and a model organization of the internal theater space, the subject of controversy and imitation.

The English principle of pluralism affects all areas. At the same time, the plural and the different are clothed in culture in separate, particular forms of existence. It has

long been known that the British are united only by war. In everyday life, however, everyone is assigned their own place, their own "island" in the general system of forms of existence. First of all, this refers to the structure of society.

The British achieve enrollment in one class or another with the help of various complex maneuvers and feel quite comfortable getting into these closed groupings. From a psychological point of view, their behavior and style should make an impression on others that is characteristic of their social level. It is very important for an Englishman to feel like a member of a social group. This is why there is such a commitment to the clubbing community here.

At the same time, every person in this culture considers the right to preserve “private space” as important. Every inhabitant of England is his own island, “in his castle, the king”, and he does not allow any invasion of his own borders [4].

As noted above, English-speaking cultures are characterized by a high degree of individualism, a large horizontal distance and a small vertical distance. Equality (egalitarianism) and distance are valuable. This is manifested in the use of space - the distance between people in the process of communication. E. Hall distinguishes 1 of the 4th types of distance:

public - the distance between the speaker and the audience, suggests loud speech (often using sound reinforcement) (more than 12 feet or 360 cm) [5].

The most important role in interpersonal communication is played by personal or personal distance. E. Hall figuratively calls it bubble (bubble), in different cultures its size varies, it is greatest, respectively, in distant ones. For English-speaking cultures, the value of personal distance, or personal space, is so high that

there is a special concept - privacy - to denote it. This zone of personal autonomy manifests itself in the daily life of the British. When observing them, it becomes obvious that privacy is not an abstract concept, it is an objective reality visible to the eye. It may seem that there is an invisible circle around people that repels people as soon as they approach - they demonstrate the subtlest sense of distance.

The ideal of an Englishman is a gentleman - a person who depends only on himself. Self-restraint and restraint, self-control and self-suppression are important principles for him. The consequence of this is self-respect and the right to irony. The gentleman believes that the highly intelligent claims of the intellect should also be limited. He prefers to find his way by instinct, through inner sensations, but not by the logical chain of deduction. We find ironically recreated images of gentlemen in the "Pickwick Papers" by Charles Dickens.

If a person in critical situations shows a restrained sense of humor - this is typical in English and makes it possible to protect your inner world from the invasion of other people's influences. **British humour** carries a strong element of satire aimed at the absurdity of everyday life. Common themes include sarcasm, insults, self-deprecation, taboo subjects, puns, innuendo, wit, and the British class system [6]. These are often accompanied by a deadpan delivery which is present throughout the British sense of humour [7].

The important concepts of the English value system are common sense, practicality and moderation, which are expressed in their extreme foresight and determine the reluctance of the English to make at least one mistake, to make at least one wrong step. The Englishman often follows the rule - "You should always be prepared for any twists of

fate". Every planned event should always have an alternative option in case" the worst happens.

Unlike the Frenchman, the Englishman is inclined not so much to think as to act, so he does not strive to seek higher and final truths and thinks about what he can really do. It is no coincidence that the aphorism "knowledge is power" was proclaimed by F. Bacon, while the Frenchman R. Descartes sought truth in the abstract principle "I think-therefore I am" [8].

Science and philosophy occupy an important place in the general cultural system of England. Practice, experience, experiment and technique are key symbols of English thinking that explain the dominant importance of science as a way of exploring the world.

Since the era of the English bourgeois revolution and the industrial revolution, England has provided the world with many outstanding scientists in the fields of physics, chemistry, astronomy, medicine, philosophy and genetics.

British philosophy has a very long, literally centuries-old tradition. Its origins are in the Middle Ages and are associated with the names of Ionnes Scott Eriugena, the Irish philosopher, and Anselm of Canterbury, the founding philosopher of scholasticism. One of the most popular philosophers of the 20th century is Bertrand Russell, known for his works related to the defense of pacifism, atheism, and leftist trends in politics.

In the 14-15th centuries. - W.Hilbert explores geomagnetism. Hilbert was the first in England to support the heliocentric teachings of Copernicus and the conclusion of Giordano Bruno that the sun is only one of the countless stars in the universe. Gilbert died in London (or Colchester) on November 30, 1603.

Thomas More became the founder of utopian socialism. Among the topics

discussed by More in *Utopia* were penology, state-controlled education, religious pluralism, divorce, euthanasia, and women's rights. The resulting demonstration of his learning, invention, and wit established his reputation as one of the foremost humanists. Soon translated into most European languages, *Utopia* became the ancestor of a new literary genre, the utopian romance [9].

Isaac Newton's discovery of the law of universal gravitation became the foundation of the European mechanistic picture of the world until the end of the 19th century. Newton made seminal contributions to several other scientific disciplines. In his book the *Principia* or "Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy, «which was published in 1687, Newton formulated the

laws of motion and universal gravitation and is considered to have laid the foundations for classical mechanics. He also introduced the notion of a Newtonian fluid, studied the speed of sound, and developed an empirical law of cooling among other major contributions made to scientific discovery. Newton's image appeared on the Bank of England notes for about 10 years in the 1970s and 1980s. He has also been commemorated on various stamp and coins [10].

Like most educators, Locke, in his understanding of society, proceeded from the recognition of the private interests of individuals. Law, according to Locke, must ensure the possibility of gaining benefits for everyone, without violating the freedom and private interests of everyone else [11].

REFERENCES:

1. Budnik G.A., Koroleva T.V. *Culturology: Ivanovo State Power Engineering University named after V.I. Lenin*. - Ivanovo, 2018. -9 p.
2. Kasyanov V.V., *Culturology: textbook. manual for higher education*. - Rostov: Phoenix, 2010. -574 p.
3. Timko, N.V. *The factor "culture" in translation*. - 2nd ed., Supplemented. - Kursk: Kursk. state un-t, 2007. -13 p.
4. Turdiyev B. S. *The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal* //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 229-233.
5. *Cultural features of English-speaking peoples*. //https://studopedia.net/5_42985_kulturnie-osobennosti-angloyazichnih-narodov.html
6. *History of English Humour, Vol. 1*, by Alfred Guy Kingan L'Estrange, 1878. // https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/18300
7. *History of English Humour, Vol. 2*, by Alfred Guy Kingan L'Estrange, 1878. // https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/18906
8. Hertogh C. P. *Thought ExpEriment Analyses of René Descartes' Cogito*. //Trans/Form/Ação, Marília, v. 39, n. 3, p. 9-22, Jul./Set., 2016.
9. *Thomas More: English humanist and statesman*. // https://www.britannica.com/biography/Thomas-More-English-humanist-and-statesman
10. Renzo Shamey. *Newton, (Sir) Isaac*. //Encyclopedia of Color Science and Technology, New York 2015. -p.5.
11. Popova E. V. *Culturology*. Ekaterinburg: Publishing house of GOU VPO "Ros. state prof.-ped. un-t", 2009. -p.198.
12. Yasavievna, Shigabutdinova Dina. "The Concept Of Culture In English Philosophy". *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol 27.1* (2021).
13. <https://www.learnenglish.de/britishculture.html>
14. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=jasur+kamolov&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&u=%23p%3DZBz14AN5I84J